

Mushroom Protein

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LIKE-A-PRO is a EU-funded project aiming to facilitate sustainable and healthy diets by mainstreaming alternative proteins and products, making them more available, accessible and acceptable.

Mushroom Protein Benefits

Cultivated mushroom proteins are those protein-rich concentrates extracted from edible mushrooms, providing a complete amino acid profile, and a source of bioactive compounds (e.g., β -glucans) which provide antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial properties and a prebiotic potential. Mushroom proteins can be obtained from cultivated biomass and non-marketable residues such as stems and malformed or leftover fruiting bodies, as they are by-products rich in proteins that offer a valorisation pathway while supporting circularity.

These non-marketable leftovers correspond to around 60,000-250,000 tonnes in Europe annually, leveraging a promising revalorisation potential.

Extraction Challenges

Current approaches for mushroom protein extraction face several limitations including low recovery rate, often below 10%, high dependence on species-specific parameters, complex solid-liquid separation and intensive operations in terms of energy and water consumption.

Funded by
the European Union

Optimised Extraction Process

As part of LIKE-A-PRO project, **CTICH** focused on optimising the valorisation of mushroom stems generated during the preparation of marketable fruiting bodies of *A. bisporus*, *P. ostreatus*, and *L. edodes* for protein extraction with the aim of maximising yield and protein content while ensuring protein quality and functionality. This was achieved through the development of a novel 6 steps extraction method which was further scaled achieving an increased extraction yield and an increased protein content from *A. bisporus* on semi-pilot conditions (around 400L).

CTICH process was proven as a new circular valorisation route for available underutilised mushroom biomass with the following characteristics:

High economic viability and alignment with consumer demand

An associated strong **cost reduction of over 97%** through significant reduction in energy demand. Alignment with **growing consumer demand** for sustainable, ethical, and natural protein alternatives that enable clean-label food formulations.

Reliable and underutilised feedstock supply

High availability of fresh mushroom stems and **discarded fruiting bodies** (around 60,000-250,000 tonnes in Europe annually).

Technical feasibility

The extraction process is technically feasible at semi-pilot scale, particularly for *A. bisporus* extracts, which is the most cultivated edible mushroom with a **38% of global share**.

Strong nutritional and functionality performance

The resulting protein concentrate powders offer high-protein content (>40%), a **complete amino acid profile**, **bioactive compounds**, **good digestibility** and **functional versatility** for food applications, including **meat analogues**, **hybrid products** and **ready meals**.

To translate this technical solution into market adoption, CTICH business model is built on a **non-exclusive licensing strategy**, transferring its proprietary known-how, initially protected as trade secret and potentially strengthened through patenting once specific optimised processes are validated, to industrial customers. This approach may be supported by optional R&D services tailored to customer needs to drive interest and early adoption. With continued upscaling, a phased roadmap foresees **commercial deployment for this process within ~8 years**, including process optimisation, industry engagement, investment, and Novel Food approval of the protein ingredient.

This project is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101083961. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.